

Figure S1. Association Between Serum CTRP9 Concentration and Other Variables Among All Participants. Scatterplots showing associations between serum CTRP9 concentration and levels of age (A), fasting glucose (B), and TG (C), respectively. Abbreviations: TG, triglyceride; CTRP9, C1q/TNF related protein 9.